

SPEAK AND WRITE WITH CONFIDENCE: INNOVATIVE PRACTICES AND TRENDS

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ABSTRACT: This article focuses on importance of speaking and writing skills. It will explain beneficial sides of them. To develop writing and speaking style in various ways, useful guides, to be able to apply these two aspects correctly not only in educational courses, however also with friends and family members. It is necessary to practice writing and speaking skills in other languages, and then the result will be satisfactory.

Keywords: interactive methods, vocabulary, communication skills.

INTRODUCTION

Good communication is the key to success, whether you're speaking in front of a large audience or trying to get a point across to a new friend. If you want to know how to speak well and confidently, you've got to believe in yourself, speak slowly and carefully, and have strong convictions about what you're saying.

“Writing skills are specific abilities which help writers put their thoughts into words in a meaningful form and to mentally interact with the message. Writing is a medium of human communication that represents language and emotion with signs and symbols. In most languages, writing is a complement to speech or spoken language. Writing is not a language, but a tool used to make languages be read. Writing skills are an important part of communication. Good writing skills allow one to communicate one’s message with clarity and ease to a far larger audience than

through face-to-face or telephone conversations. In its most advanced form, written expression can be as vivid as a work of art.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

1. Speaking

State your opinions with conviction. Before you speak, you have to make sure you really believe in what you say, whether you're saying that Kanye's new album is amazing or that the growing inequality gap in the United States should be the government's concern. You don't have to sound arrogant to get your point across and to sound like you really believe in what you're saying instead of turning to other people for validation or approval.

Make eye contact. For one thing, it is polite for others. Also, eye contact will help others to listen to your thinking carefully. Find a few friendly faces to focus on so your confidence goes up while you're speaking and that you're communicating your message even more clearly. If you look down at the floor, you won't look confident, and if you're looking around while you talk, people may think that you're distracted or looking for something better to do.

Look people in the eyes when you talk to them you can look away for a moment or two to get your footing, but in general, stay focused on the eyes of the people you're talking to.

If you see someone looking confused or concerned when you're speaking, you may even think about whether or not you're being clear enough. However, you shouldn't let one confused person get you off track.

If you're talking to a larger group where it's difficult to really make eye contact, focus on looking at just a few people in the audience.

Know the room. Arrive early, walk around the speaking area and practice using the microphone and any visual aids. Knowing what you're up against and having a sense of where you'll stand, how the crowd will look, and what it will feel like to move around as you speak can definitely ease your nerves. It's far better to know what you're facing than to have a big surprise -- and a blow to your confidence -- on the day of the big event.

If you really want to know the room, you can also show up on a day before your actual speaking engagement to get a sense of what it's like.

2 WRITING

Characteristics of Good Writing Skills

In every workplace, workers are always writing notes, emails, memos, letters, and reports. All of these require good writing skills so that people can communicate their ideas effectively. So one must possess the following characteristics for effective writing.

1. Clarity and focus:

In good writing, everything makes sense, and readers don't get lost or have to reread passages to figure out what's going on. Thus one must focus on writing sticks with the plot or core idea without running off on too many tangents.

2. Organization:

A well-organized piece of writing is not only clear, but it's also presented in a way that is logical and aesthetically pleasing.

3. Ideas and themes:

Is the topic of your paper relevant? Does your story come complete with themes? Can the reader visualize your poem? For a piece of writing to be considered well crafted, it has to contain clearly identifiable ideas and themes.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, while both writing and speaking are important forms of communication, they have different strengths and are best suited for different situations. Writing is well suited for more formal and permanent forms of communication, while speaking is better for more informal and immediate interactions. Both have their own place in communication and it's important to know when to use them to express oneself effectively.

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